

Volume 9, Number 1, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN SHOMOLU LGA, LAGOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Increasing waste generation in most urban area creates visible economic, social and environmental problems with municipal authorities lacking the capacity to cope with their removal as a result of inadequate funds and other bottle necks. This study sought to identify the challenges and opportunities in municipal solid waste management in Shomolu LGA of Lagos State. Data were gathered through questionnaire survey and stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select household units among the settlement clusters while purposeful and accidental sampling methods were adopted to select 300 respondents from the settlements under study. Lagos State waste Management Authority (LAWMA) members of staff that are directly involved in waste management numbering 34 were purposively selected for questionnaire administration. Fifty (50) waste pickers who volunteered to be part of the study were selected. The study revealed the challenges for both households and waste pickers to include lack of adherence to the schedule for waste collection and disposal, insufficient waste storage containers served to households, stigmatization, harassment and occupational hazards of injuries and ailments. While for the waste management authority the challenges are operational which include logistics problem, poor remuneration, and poor public attitude towards operators and poor infrastructure among others. The results also indicated that the opportunities associated with waste management include material recovery, reduction in environmental pollution, income generation and livelihood security for the urban poor, reduction in the waste stream that would have been collected and disposed off in dumpsites and reduction in the cost of waste management. The study recommended payment of compensation to waste pickers for the environmental services rendered, improved budgetary allocation to waste management authority to increase their efficiency, promulgation of laws to protect the rights of waste pickers and provision of protective equipment to reduce work place occupational hazards.*

Keywords: *Challenges, management, opportunities, solid Waste, Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

It is widely acknowledged that solid waste management (SWM) is one of the biggest challenges facing municipal authorities across the globe (Khatib, 2011; Wilson et al., 2012; Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012;

Tacoli, 2012; Guerrero et al. 2013; UNEP, 2013; Aliu et al., 2014; Harir et al., 2015; Njoku et al., 2015; Nyampundu et al., 2020) while factors such as population growth, urbanization, economic growth and industrialization often contribute to an

increasing volume of solid waste generated (Myers and Kent, 2003; Vergara and Tchobanoglous, 2013; Xiao et al., 2020).

The United Nation Environmental Programme (UNEP, 2020 and Sharma et al. (2020) acknowledged the inability of most municipal authorities in the collection and disposal of solid waste probably due to inadequate financial resources and infrastructure for the change in the dynamics of the waste generation leading to increased waste mismanagement, thereby resulting in pollution. Challenges of poor waste management in the developing countries and sub-Saharan African in particular include amongst others weak organizational structures, lack of appropriate skills, inadequate budgets, weak legislation, lack of enforcement, low public awareness, corruption, conflict, political instability, lack of political will and essentially at the heart of the problem is the failure in governance (Godfrey et al., 2019).

The inadequacies in the management of municipal solid waste (MSW) is represented by low rate of collection, dumping and accumulation of waste on the streets and roadsides, overflowing public collection /skip containers and the indiscriminate dumping of waste in urban areas create risk of diseases, flooding and environmental pollution while burning of waste in open spaces causes significant air pollution which impacts human health and contributes to changing climates (Ahmed and Ali, 2004; Scheinberg et al., 2010; Wilson et al., 2012; Okot-Okumu, 2012; Lederer et al., 2015; Suleman, Darko, Agyemang-Duah, 2015; UNEP, 2015; Ziraba, Haregu, Mberu, 2016; Moss, Eidson, Jambeck, 2017). The impacts of poor waste management on public health and the environment have been widely documented (Sridevi, Modi, Lakshmi and Kesavarao,

2012; Annepu, 2012; Dasgupta, Yadav and Mondal, 2013; Srivastava, Krishna and Sonkar, 2014; Maheshwari, Gupta and Das, 2015; Aminuddin and Rahman, 2015; Ziraba, Haregu and Mberu, 2016; Mamady, 2016; Gutberlet and Uddin, 2017).

Available records showed that 125 million tons of municipal solid waste (MSW) was generated per annum in Africa in 2012 out of which sub-Saharan Africa accounted for 81 million tons with a percentage value of (65%). This is projected to increase to 244 million tons per year by 2025 and following an average waste collection rate of only 55% (68 million tons) nearly half of all MSW generated in Africa remains uncollected within our cities and towns mostly dumped onto sidewalks, open fields, storm water drains and rivers (Scarlat, 2015). Estimates shows 80–90% of the MSW generated in Africa is composed of recyclable with an average of 57% of the waste being wet biodegradable organic waste, while 13% is plastic, paper 9%, glass 4%, metal 4% with others of textiles, construction and demolition waste etc recorded 13% and presents the opportunity of waste recycling as a secondary resource since only 4% of the waste generated in Africa is currently recycled (Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012; Van Wyk, 2018).

Open waste dumps and unsanitary landfills provides eminent scope for itinerant waste pickers to recover valuable recyclables for their livelihood and this informal recycling reduces the associated environmental pollution from waste in the landfills and adds value to the recycling sector while harnessing increased informal employability opportunities (Fei et al., 2016; Aparcana, 2017). Waste management approach with emphasis laid on 3Rs (reduce, reuse and recycle) of bio-degradable and non-biodegradable waste represent a major economic opportunity to society since it contributes to

reduction in the cost of raw material, energy and labour (Rao, Otoo and Hanjra, 2017). Morris (1996) reported that recycling of mixed solid waste conserves energy that would have been used in extracting natural resources and transforming them to produce goods that can also be manufactured from recycled materials as well as generates income to the many actors along the value chain. Currently global solid waste generation is 2.01 billion tons and is expected to grow to 3.4 billion tons by 2050 (Kaza et al., 2018) and this scenario provides insight into the opportunities inherent in each component of waste as a result of paradigm shift from the depletive 'produce, consume and dispose' model of the linear economy to the 'reduce, reuse, recover, recycle, redesign and remake' model of the circular economy (CE). Integration of circular economy approach in solid waste management system holds particular promise for the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 12 (SDG12) particularly the realization of Target 12.5 which is to substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse by 2030.

Several studies have been undertaken in parts of Lagos State in relation to solid waste management and those whose focus was on household knowledge and perception of solid waste management are recorded in the works of Longe, Longe and Ukpebor (2009) and Adeniran and Oyemade (2016). Research efforts has also focused on the challenges of solid waste management as exemplified by the works of Afon (2012), Aderogba and Afelumo (2012), Adejobi and Olorunnimbe (2012), Aderemi and Otitolaju (2012), Adewole (2013), Ayantoyinbo and Adepoju (2018), Taleat and Benson (2019) and Mba and Nnadi (2022). There are also studies on performance assessment of solid waste management following the adoption of public private partnership in solid waste management in

Lagos and this is showed in the works of Idowu, Omirin and Osagie (2011), Agboje, Adeoti and Irhivben (2014), Aliu, Adeyemi and Adebayo (2014), Anestina, Adetola, and Odafe (2014), and Olukanni and Oresanya (2018). Opportunities in reclaiming value from solid waste so as to help people who lack resources have been under researched with available literature on waste recycling and urban governance in Lagos by Nzeadibe and Iwuoha (2008), Nzeadibe and Ajaero (2010) and Ogbonna and Mikailu (2019).

It is important to conduct studies that will identify the opportunities associated with solid waste management in a circular economy that conserves resources with a huge potential for job and wealth creation, poverty reduction and livelihood security in Lagos state. No specific studies have been done in Shomolu to identify the challenges and opportunities in municipal solid waste management. Hence studying this fills the current gap in knowledge and could lead to improved solid waste management practice. It is widely acknowledged that informal sector operators plays a very active role in the collection and diversion of reusable and recyclable waste materials away from dumpsites and landfills in the process of resource recovery to help meet the growing demands for raw materials and the reduction of significant amount of waste while also unlocking opportunities that ensures improved livelihoods as well as create many direct jobs and even more indirect and induced employment opportunities with reasonable compensations.

This study will contribute to increasing our knowledge on the opportunities associated with waste management in a circular economy rather than the linear economy that promote wastages. The justification for this study is ascribed to the challenges of environmental protection, public health as well as waste reduction and material

recovery from mixed waste stream. Following the projected increase in waste generation and the exponential growth in population make the research important and timely.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Shomolu is one of the 20 Local Government Areas of Lagos State and it is located between latitudes 6°31'20"N and 6°33'20"N and longitudes 3°22'0"E and 3°24'0"E. Major communities/administrative wards that make up Shomolu

include Onipanu, Okesuna/Alase, Igbari, Fadeyi/Igboji, Bashua, Orile/Alade, Bajulaiye and Ijebu-Tedo as shown on Figure 1. The study area experiences tropical wet and dry climate with two distinct rainy seasons which is more intense between April and July and milder from October to November. The highest temperature is recorded in the month of March with average daytime temperature of 32°C. There is a decrease in temperature during the rainy season due to dense cloud cover between April and November as well as during the harmattan period of December to March. (Silva, 2014; Somolu – Wikipedia, 2023).

Figure 1: Location of the Study Area
 Source: Modified from Administrative Map of Lagos State

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Shomolu had a total population of 403,569 people in 2006 (NPC, 2006) and copies of questionnaire were derived using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) procedure who postulated that for population sizes between 250,000 and 1,000,000, the sample size should be 384 at 5.0% margin of error and 95% confidence level. In order to achieve the aim of the study, respondents were drawn from heads of households, staff of Lagos State Waste Management Authority (LAWMA) and waste pickers. Based on the settlement size and composition of household dwellings, stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select household units among the settlement clusters of Onipanu, Okesuna/Alase, Fadeyi/Igbobi, Bashua and Bajulaiye for the study while purposeful and accidental (i.e., non-probability sampling technique) sampling methods were adopted to select 300 respondents from the settlements under study.

The purposefully selected respondents include estate and community leaders while the accidental samples comprised household

heads that were present and in their houses during the conduct of the survey. LAWMA members of staff that were directly involved in waste management were stratified into three categories namely low, medium and high cadre or based on GL 3-5, GL 6-10, and $GL \geq 12$ and 34 copies of questionnaire were purposefully administered. Waste picking activities is unregistered and unregulated and waste pickers mostly work independently and hence lack a sampling frame, a sample size of 50 waste pickers who volunteered to be part of the study were selected and involved in the survey.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data generated from the questionnaire were summarized using descriptive statistics and cross-tabulations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

The demographic characteristics of the sampled respondents in this study centered on age, gender and educational qualifications and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	Heads of households (no=300)		Waste pickers (no=50)		LAWMA staff (no=34)		TOTAL (no =384)	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq	%
Gender								
Male	121	40.3	46	92.0	24	70.6	191	49.7
Female	179	59.7	4	8.0	10	29.4	193	50.3
Age								
10-20	0	0.0	4	8.0	0	0.0	4	1.0
21-30	0	0.0	36	72.0	15	44.1	51	13.3
31-40	48	16.0	10	20.0	9	26.5	67	17.4
41-50	90	30.0	0	0.0	7	20.6	97	25.3
51-60	95	31.7	0	0.0	3	8.8	98	25.5
61 ≥	67	22.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	67	17.4
Educational qualification								
Primary	64	21.3	11	22.0	6	17.6	81	21.1
Secondary	158	52.7	0	0.0	18	52.9	176	45.8
Tertiary	41	13.7	0	0.0	10	29.4	51	13.3
No formal Educ.	37	12.3	39	78.0	0	0.0	76	19.8

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2023

The study revealed that 40.3% of the household heads that serves as respondents were male while 59.7% were female. The reasons for this could be a mixed factor of more property owners being female and others may have been widowed. The observed dominance of female over male further confirmed that the responsibility of environmental sanitation and waste disposal is majorly the activities of women in sub-Saharan Africa. The study also revealed as captured in Table 1, the profile of the waste pickers and scavengers with the statistics showing that male waste pickers were 92.0% while 8.0% are female. Waste picking is attractive to both gender but because of the tedious nature of the job the occupation is predominantly dominated by the male gender. The result of study is in agreement with the finding of Abu and Michael (2018) and Ogwueleka and Naveen (2021) who reported male dominance in waste picking activities. It is also evident from the study that the LAWMA members of staff directly responsible for waste management in relation to collection and final disposal are mostly male.

The study also revealed that 16.0 % of the

household heads that served as respondents were averagely 40 years old, while 30.0% were between 41-50 years old. Household heads within the age of 51-60 constitute the majority at 31.7% while 61 and above age bracket accounted for 22.3% of the respondents. It can be deduced from the study that the average age of 50 years represents engagement as household heads and experience in environmental management related issues of solid waste as well as in advantage position to explain the challenges of waste management in their neighbourhood.

The study also revealed the age of the informal sector engagement of respondents in waste picking activities with the bracket of 10-20 years represented by 8.0%, 21-30 years at 72.0% while 31-40 years recorded 20.0%. The study of Ogwueleka and Naveen (2021) also reported that that the scavengers are quite young. The respondents' age could also be a reflection that they have acquired varying lengths of job experience in this informal employment that provides opportunities for many urban poor through the recovery of recyclable materials. It is also arguable that the high level of

unemployment in the formal sector of the Nigerian economy may be responsible for waste pickers seeking livelihood and economic safety net from waste picking as a means to survive and earn daily income to meet the demands of the family. With regards to the LAWMA staff members as revealed by the study, their ages are also a reflection of their grade levels and length of service in their employment. The study also revealed the educational attainments of heads of household and LAWMA line staff members saddled with waste management in the study area. Those with primary certificates are 21.3% and 17.6% respectively, secondary certificates are 52.7% and 52.9% respectively while those that possessed tertiary certificates are represented by 13.7% and 29.4% respectively. Heads of household with no formal education accounted for 12.3%. The level of educational attainment is an indicator that points to the awareness and understanding of the respondents on the linkages between poor waste management and public health and also the willpower to adopt efficient and sustainable

methods of waste management that would reduce the impact of poor waste management on public health is easier and faster among the educated households than the uneducated ones. For the waste pickers, 22% attended primary school while 78.0% had no formal education. The structure of informal waste picking is composed of scavengers whose aim is targeted at recovery, reuse and sales of recyclable materials and since their activities are labour intensive, unregulated with low technology application it attracts unskilled people with low educational background as a result of the monetary benefits which they can easily get without any qualifications or going through any formal employment processes. Abu and Michael (2018) also reported that waste pickers are known to be unskilled have with low literacy levels.

METHODS OF WASTE DISPOSAL BY HOUSEHOLDS AND COLLECTION BY WASTE PICKERS

The respondents’ household methods of waste disposal and avenues for recyclable waste collection by scavengers are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Method of disposal of waste and collection of recyclable waste

Characteristics	Heads of households (no=300)		Waste pickers (no =50)	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Methods of households solid waste disposal/ collection by waste pickers				
Residential litter bin	52	17.3	6	12.0
Public collection /skip containers	38	12.7	8	16.0
Street/road side dump	200	66.7	32	64.0
Burning of waste	10	3.3	0	0.0
Designated dump site	0	0.0	4	8.0

Source: Author’s Fieldwork, 2023

Assessment of sampled household with regards to methods of households’ solid waste disposal facilities used to ensure safe sanitation reveals that households employed use of residential litter/waste bin, public collection /skip

containers, indiscriminate dumping on the street/road side dump and burning of waste. The study revealed that residential litter bin whereby resident dispose off their waste using litter bin, waste bag and drums recorded 17.3% usage,

while public collection/skip containers where waste is been disposed off with the help of collection truck is represented by 12.7%. Indiscriminate dumping where resident put together waste and throws them off on the streets, road side or drainage system recorded 66.7% and burning of waste whereby waste are been brought out and set on fire recorded 3.3%. Also revealed were that waste picker recovers recyclable materials by sorting and segregation of mixed waste and the statistics shows that recyclable materials recovered from residential litter bin recorded 12.0%, public collection /skip containers are represented by 16.0%, street/road side dump as well as designated or illegal dump sites is represented by 64.0% and 8.0% respectively. It is important to note that the predominant waste disposal method in Nigerian cities is open and indiscriminate dumping and this has made waste readily available for scavengers.

The study of Medina (2000) also revealed that informal waste pickers recover recyclable materials from the streets, landfill sites, dumps and from households in some cases. The composition of household or municipal solid

wastes ranging from food waste, plastics, wood, metals, papers, rubbers, leather, textiles, demolition and construction waste etc offers opportunities for resource recovering and recycling with waste pickers mainly involved in the sorting and segregation of the collected waste. In most middle and low-income countries where government and municipalities have not made significant investment in waste management, recycling as a vital waste management component is carried on by the informal waste pickers who earn a living through informal waste collection and recycling thereby contributing to resource material input of recyclable materials to local manufacturing industries at reduced cost.

CHALLENGES IN MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

The perceived challenges confronting households, waste pickers and the waste management authority in the day-to-day management of solid waste are presented in Table 3. Challenges for the household are in relation to frequency of waste collection and disposal as well as provision and adequacy of garbage storage containers.

Table 3: Respondents perceived challenges of municipal solid waste management

Characteristics	Heads of households (no=300)		Characteristics	Heads of households (no=300)	
	Freq.	%		Freq.	%
Frequency of household solid waste collection and disposal			Sufficiency of garbage storage containers		
Daily	0	0.0	Adequate	61	20.3
Once in a week	21	7.0	Inadequate	194	64.7
Once in 2 weeks	46	15.3	Not available	45	15.0
Once in 3 weeks	55	18.3			
Monthly	178	59.3			
Not at all	0	0.0			
Characteristics	Waste pickers (no=50)		Characteristics	Waste pickers (no=50)	
	Freq.	%		Freq.	%
Stigmatization			Injuries associated with waste picking		
Low self esteem	10	20.0	Bottle cut injuries	38	76.0
Harassment	35	70.0	Nail injuries	8	16.0
Branding as thieves	5	10.0	Injuries from used syringes/needle	4	8.0
Characteristics	Waste pickers (no=50)		Characteristics	LAWMA staff (no=34)	
	Freq.	%		Freq.	%
Ailments experienced by waste picker			LAWMA challenges in waste collection and disposal		
Respiratory problem	8	16.0	Logistics problem	11	32.0
Body rash/ Body pains	26	52.0	Poor remuneration	5	14.7
Eye irritation	6	12.0	Poor public attitude towards operators	3	8.8
Cholera/Diarrhea/dysentery	10	20.0	Poor infrastructure/ Bad roads	8	23.5
			Weather challenges	2	5.9
			Insufficient waste bin/storage containers	5	14.7

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2023

For households served with waste storage bin, the system of waste collection is mainly door-to-door collection with the services of a collection truck and the study shows that weekly collection is 7.0%, once in 2 weeks is 15.3%, and once in 3 weeks is 18.3% while on monthly basis is 59.3%. With regards to the sufficiency of garbage storage containers, 20.3% of the respondents perceived that it is adequate, 64.75% submitted that it is inadequate, while 15% were not served with garbage containers. On the average the frequency of waste collection and provision of

garbage storage facilities is a challenge. The composition of the equipment and infrastructure is a pointer to the effectiveness of waste management and the municipality has made little to non-improvements in the area of garbage and skips bins for storage of waste in public places.

The study also revealed the impediments of waste pickers' involvement in informal waste Picking and recycling to include different level of stigmatization with low self-esteem represented by 20.0%, harassment at 70.0%

and branding as thieves recorded 10.0%; injuries recorded as bottle cut 76.0%, nail injuries recorded 16.0% and injuries from used syringes/needle recorded 8.0%. Major ailments experienced include respiratory problem 16.0%, body rash/ body pains 52.0%, eye irritation 12.0% and cholera/diarrhea/dysentery at 20.0%. Findings from the study of Chokhandre, Singh and Kashyap (2017) also reported some injuries and prevalence of diseases. Waste pickers involvement in informal waste picking and recycling is bedeviled with a number of impediments and majority of them are the challenges they face in their line of operations. Predominantly waste picking is carried on at residential and neighbourhood litter bins, commercial places, in the streets and roadside dumps as well as in dumpsites. All the modes of sourcing for reusable materials expose them to intimidation, harassment and stigmatization from individuals, the authorities and the public probably because of their appearance and their association with waste. They also experience varying degrees of injuries because most waste pickers use their hands with no protective equipment in searching, sorting and segregation of recyclable materials as well as risk of contracting diseases as a result of their poor knowledge of sanitation and hygiene, occupational health and safety. The study

revealed the challenges of LAWMA as a stakeholder in waste management in the municipality to include logistics problem 32.0%, poor remuneration 14.7%, and poor public attitude towards operators 8.8 %, poor infrastructure / bad roads 23.5%, weather challenges 5.9 % and insufficient waste bin/storage containers 14.7%. The operational challenges facing the waste management authority are quite enormous particularly with respect to the number of vehicles available for solid waste collection, poor state of road infrastructure and insufficient facilities. All these may be accountable for deficiencies observed with the waste collection and disposal schedule.

OPPORTUNITIES IN MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

The opportunities derivable from municipal solid waste management are as a result of the inclusiveness of circular economy principles of the 3Rs (recycling, reuse and recovery) with the target of reduction in extraction of resources as well as eliminate waste and pollution so as to ensure environmental Sustainability. The study revealed the benefits of waste picking and recycling activities on income and the environment and these are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Benefits of informal sector waste picking and recycling activities on income and the environment

Characteristics	Waste pickers (no=50)		Characteristics	Waste pickers (no=50)	
	Freq.	%		Freq.	%
Reasons of involvement in waste recycling			Types of reusable waste collected		
Economic/livelihood	50	100.0	Plastic/PET bottles/ rubber	15	30.0
Environmental sanitation/cleanliness	0	0.0	Paper	4	8.0
Quantity of reusable waste collected per day			Metal scrap materials	23	46.0
1-4kg	0	0.0	Glass/bottles	8	16.0
5-8 kg	11	22.0	Price per kg of reusable waste		
9-12 kg	13	26.0	Plastics (₦250.00)	15	30.0
13-16 kg	21	42.0	Paper (₦200.00)	4	8.0
Above 16kg	5	10.0	Metal scraps (₦300.00)	23	46.0
Average monthly income			Glass/bottle (₦200.00)	8	16.0
₦1,000-₦5,000	0	0.0	Environmental benefit of waste picking/recycling		
₦6,000-₦10,000	0	0.0	Pollution reduction	15	30.0
₦11,000-₦15,000	0	0.0	Waste reduction	10	20.0
₦16,000-₦20,000	0	0.0	Material recovery	25	50.0
₦21,000-₦25,000	0	0.0			
₦26,000-₦30,000	0	0.0			
>₦30,000	50	100.0			
100.0					

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2023

Assessment of the sampled respondents with regards to reasons for involvement in waste recycling showed that all the respondents (100.0%) is for economic reasons and that is to say the major stimulus for informal waste pickers' engagement is poverty alleviation and the financial reward accruable to unskilled individual engaged in waste picking. Essentially most urban poor see waste picking as a source of livelihood and the remuneration realized from waste picking is used for their family upkeep. They could also apply the money as start-up capital for other businesses to sustain themselves. The demand for specific recyclable and the price the middlemen and the junk shop dealers are willing to offer determines the types of recyclables collected by waste pickers. The study of Medina (2000) also affirmed that most waste pickers were interested in waste of high earning.

It is evident from the study that the recyclable

collected are in the categories of plastic/PET bottles/ rubber 30.0%, paper 8.0%, scrap metal materials 46.0% and glass/bottles 16.0% while the amount paid for a kilogram of recyclable is metal scraps (₦300.00), plastics (₦250.00), paper (₦200.00) and glass/bottle (₦200.00) and this has made metal scrap most sorted after in the waste stream. It is evident from the haulage and transportation of truckloads of scrap metals and other recyclables that there has been a growing demand for material recovery, reuse and recycling in Lagos particularly for utensils and other household manufacture, in metal conversion industries, plastic/polythene and packaging material production, recycling of newspapers into tissue paper, newsprint and other bulk packaging materials as well as recycling of bottles and glass production. Waste picking engagement of the urban poor operates on daily wages and waste pickers work for longer hours to gather tons of waste on the basis

of the more you pick, the more you earn. The study revealed the quantity of recyclable collected per day and this is mostly influenced by factors such as trekking distance to locate material, age and sex, health status of the picker, material type and collection methods among others. The quantity collected ranges from 5-8 kg, 9-12 kg, 13-16 kg and above 16kg with percentage recovery represented by 22.0%, 26.0%, 42.0% and 10.0% respectively.

Waste scavenging represents an income generating activity and livelihood security for the urban poor and the wages received from its operation is comparable and, in some instances, surpasses the minimum wage in the formal and organized sector of the economy. The average monthly income of a waste picker was calculated by multiplying the total kilogram of waste on a daily basis by the unit price per kilogram to arrive at the monthly income using a base of 21 working days in a month. The monthly income per head of a plastic waste picker ranges from ₦42,000.00- ₦84,000.00 while that of a paper waste picker range from ₦36,600.00- ₦67,200.00, the income of a scrap metal waste picker ranges from ₦54,400.00- ₦100,800.00, while that of a glass/ bottle waste picker range from ₦33,600.00- ₦67,200.00. The result revealed that monthly income of waste pickers is more in comparison with the 2019 approved thirty-thousand-naira (₦30,000.00) baseline national minimum wage for federal work per month. The study of Abu and Michael (2018) also reported that 34.7% of the waste pickers earn above the national minimum wage.

Also revealed is that picking of recyclable materials contributes to pollution reduction by 30.0%, waste reduction by 20.0% and material recovery by 50.0%. Scholars have acknowledged the importance of circular economy approach to waste management and the environmental, economic, and social benefits of informal waste

scavenging activities has been documented and not only does waste recycling reduces environmental pollution of air and water, it also conserves energy and resources applied to producing new raw materials, provides cheaper raw materials and reduces imports of raw materials for industrial manufactures. In addition, through material recovery from the waste stream, it contributes to reduction in the amount of waste that would have been collected, transported and disposed off in dumpsites and landfills and translates to reduction in the cost of waste management for the municipality.

IMPLICATIONS OF MANAGEMENT AND RECYCLING OF SOLID WASTE

Taking a standpoint from the perspective of waste management value chain, introduction of service fees or increase in charges for waste collection and disposal may likely encourage households to practice waste sorting and segregation as a means of minimizing waste generation thereby creating wealth from waste valorization. It has been reported and documented that some of the problems associated with polluted environments as a result of waste accumulation include disturbing odour, leachate which contaminates both land and surface water and also provide breeding grounds for flies, rodents and other insects pests (Maheshwari, Gupta and Das, 2015; Lee et al, 2016; Mamady, 2016; Gutberlet and Uddin, 2017; Norsa'adah, Salinah, Naing and Sarimah, 2020).

Beyond the concentration of carbon dioxide, emission of methane and other greenhouse gases into the atmosphere from waste dumps that contribute to climate change, exposure to gases generated from landfill has some health implications (EPQS, 2009; Lee et al, 2016). Poor management of waste had also been reported as one of the causes of blocked drains and the

resulting flooding in most cities (Kaza, Yao, Bhada-Tata and Woerden, 2018; Tsydenova, Morillas, Salas, 2018). It is important to note that waste pickers activities of collection of recyclables materials accrue economic benefits to them as well as contribute to reduction of waste accumulation in the municipalities and communities they operate. Despite these benefits, their activities go unnoticed and uncompensated for and they face several challenges.

In acknowledging the role the informal waste pickers play in waste management as well as the economic and environmental benefits of waste material recycling there is need to create an enabling environment for their operations in terms of interventions in providing them with personal protective equipment so as to minimize the occupational hazards associated with waste scavenging activities and also enact laws protecting their human rights and the implementation of such laws to curtail the harassment, intimidation and stigmatization they face from the public. Experience as shown that collective bargaining achieves desired result under organized trade union therefore organizing them into such association and backed by law will contribute in no small measure to ensure their welfare and wellbeing.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study underscores the importance of informal sector waste pickers in waste management and material recycling from mixed waste stream provides opportunities to earn income with positive environmental impacts such contribution to reduction of materials disposed in sanitary landfills, reduction of energy expenses and cost of extraction of natural resources regardless the enormous challenges of municipal solid waste management. Despite the social injustice, inequality and vulnerability of the waste pickers,

waste recycling provides a window for conservation of natural resources and poverty alleviation. Recommendations made based on the findings are an appropriate and consistent amount of compensation should be paid to waste pickers for the positive environmental externality of their services, improved budgetary allocation to waste management authority to increase their efficiency, introduction and implementation of legislative and legal frameworks to protect the rights of waste pickers as well as reduce the inhuman treatments they face in the line of their duties and provision of protective gadgets to reduce the occupational hazards they are exposed to.

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